

Comparative Relationship between Parental Socio-Economic-Status and Performance among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria

Yahaya, Mohammed Ashiru¹

yashiru31@gmail.com

+2348134123553

Adeyanju, Adekunle Samuel¹

dknladeyanju@gmail.com

+2347033449254

¹Department of General Studies in Education, School of Education, Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated the influence of parental socio-economic status (income, education, occupation, involvement and cultural beliefs) on students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population covered parents and students in public senior secondary schools in the state. Simple random sampling technique was adopted for parents while multi-stage random technique was adopted for students from selected public senior secondary schools in Osun State. The total number of respondents for this study was 3,350 respondents, constituting 1,675 students and 1,675 parents. However, only 1,560 returned their instruments. The instruments used in the study were: Parental Socio-economic Status Questionnaire (PSSQ) and Academic Achievement Test (AAT) deduced from past SS III students' WAEC questions on English Language and Mathematics was administered to students who responded to (PSSQ). Results revealed a poor performance from the attainment test while cultural factors appeared to be the only predictor of academic success; income, occupation, parental involvement, academic status all had no significant relationship with students' academic performance. The reliability figures for the variables were; income status: 0.75, educational status: 0.81, Occupational status: 0.71, level of involvement: 0.70, cultural beliefs: 0.71, attainment scores: 0.75. Simple percentage, mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while regression was used for the hypothesis. Based on the findings, it was recommended that, the Governments and policymakers should ensure that schools in Osun State are adequately equipped with teaching materials. Also, there is need for an improvement in infrastructure and provision of regular professional development for teachers to support effective learning.

Keywords: Parental Socio-Economic, Students, Academic Performance.

Introduction

Poor academic performance in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in some states in Nigeria has become a matter of concern to everyone. According to Oni et al., (2016) the quality of any educational system is mostly assessed by the performance of the system's products. There is no refuting in the fact that parents are the primary persons in raising children in any society that is why the family is regarded as the primary agent of socialization. In the same vain, Ohanyelu (2022) identified the components that must come into play in the educational process which include; education, income, occupation, level of involvement and culture. Previous researches revealed that for a successful educational process to be realized, these components must be harmonized. Whatsoever affect the developmental environment of students would possibly affect their education or disposition to it. The variables that contribute effectively to quality of academic performance are found within and outside the school. Parental status is one of such variables found outside the school as posited by Eliasson et al (2020) that students with poor socio-economic background are predisposed to dearth of resources. The researcher also recognised the possibility for children from low background to compete well with their counterparts from high socio-economic background under the same academic environment.

Despite the Federal Ministry of Education and State Government's effort in funding public schools, there still exists poor academic performance among students in Osun State. This means that majority of students in this state do not attain the minimum qualification for tertiary admission which is five Credits and above including English Language and General Mathematics. According to the Federal Ministry of Education, the percentage pass rate for English and Mathematics in Osun state between 2020 and 2024 averaged 41% (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). This dismal academic performance has raised concerns for parents and other educational stakeholders considering the financial and material investment made to provide education to learners. However, enough research has not been conducted on the influence of parents' education, occupation,

income, involvement and cultural belief on students' academic performance. Against this backdrop, this study seeks to holistically examine the influence of parental socio-economic status on students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State.

This research draws heavily from Bourdieu's theory of Cultural Capital. According to Bourdieu's Cultural Capital Theory, children from higher socioeconomic backgrounds gain from cultural resources that are consistent with the standards and ideals of the educational system. These assets improve their academic success and include language skills, knowledge of academic expectations, and access to extracurricular learning activities. This is in tandem with Guttormsen and Moore (2023) who drew on Bourdieu's epistemic reflexivity, highlighting the ways in which cultural capital affects the creation of knowledge and the process of making decisions

Conceptual Framework
Socio-economic factors

Self-constructed by researcher, adapted from Meng, Q., & Zhang, Q. (2023)

Parental Income and Students' Academic Performance

A person's education is closely linked to his/her life choices, income therefore, it is important to have a clear understanding of what benefits or hinders one's educational attainment. Education is a fundamental human right, the key to sustainable development, a crucial tool for effective participation in societies and it enhances peace and stability among countries. Eliasson et al (2022) posited that students from families with high income perform better than those from low income families in the United States of America. The author posited that the impact of the Parents' income can be shown in the early timing of the students' learning.

Parental Level of Education and Students' Academic Performance

Studies have indicated that parents with higher educational status could trigger the intellectual potential of their children which leads them to perform better in school and in return strive for further education (Rana et al., 2015). Duckworth et al., (2019), Hsieh (2022), Arifin et., et (2023) and Kim et al. (2023) asserted that children of more educated parents are more likely to be enrolled and more likely to progress further through school, conversely, children of parents with lower educational attainment tend to perform poorly because of reduced parental involvement in their children's learning. Li et al., (2022) and Bhatia et al., 2023 established a connection between high parental confidence and healthy parent-child relationship which positively translates to better academic performance of their children. Educated parents are more likely to provide an atmosphere that is conducive for learning and help their children succeed academically (Tipton, 2018, Eyinade & Akharume, 2020, Covas & Veiga, 2021, Su et al., 2022, Umoru & Aboritoli, 2021).

Parental Occupation and Student's Academic Performance

The home has a significant influence on the psychological, emotional, social and economic state of the students. Naite, (2021) averred that children of bankers, doctors, and teachers probably may have a different upbringing from those children of most farmland and domestic workers. According to Mudassir and Abubakar (2015), Gutfleisch &Kogan, (2022) and Colicol&Sali-Latif (2023) the profession and socioeconomic status of parents affect the schools that a child chooses, which in turn affects academic performance and academic success. Rahaman (2023) averred that the careers and aspirations of children can also be influenced by the jobs that their parents hold. According to Chukwuorji and Nwonyi (2015), Hsieh and Simpkins (2022), Cheng & Lai (2023) and Efstratopoulou et al., (2023), anxiety levels among secondary school students during test were influenced by the jobs held by their parents.

Parent's Level of Involvement and Students' Academic Performance

Hsieh, (2023) reveals the relationship between parental participation and student engagement, showing how involvement at home and in school improves children's emotional, cognitive, and behavioural engagement—all of which are critical for success in school. Donkor (2023) revealed that the association between children's academic success and their socioeconomic status is mediated by parental support, which mitigates the adverse effects of low socioeconomic status on

academic performance. According to Georgiou (2023) and Yulianti et al., (2023) creating a home atmosphere that supports academic endeavour and establishing the importance of education are other aspects of parental participation. Likewise, Chavez et al., (2023) averred that giving emotional and psychological support to children is another aspect of parental support that may have a big impact on their academic achievement.

Cultural Beliefs and Students' Academic Performance

Certain cultures place a great emphasis on education, and parents actively encourage their children to achieve academic success by establishing high standards for them, through investment of time, resources and efforts (Kainuwa et al., 2018). Kristofferson (2023) however found out a contrary stance in which some cultural practices frown at formal education which by extension reduces the zeal for study. In like manner, Kainuwa et al., (2018) established a connection between religious and cultural beliefs and students' drop-out rate. He found out that children from families who placed credence on education regardless of cultural beliefs enjoy continued education, than the ones who placed little or no credence to education. Similarly, the educational expectations of children of migrants in China and discovered that parental beliefs controlled the children's access to family resources, which in turn had a major impact on their academic ambitions.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives designed to guide the study.

1. To examine the level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State.
2. To ascertain the level of parental education of public secondary school students in Osun State
3. To ascertain the nature of parental occupation of public secondary school students in Osun State
4. To determine the level of parental income of public secondary school students in Osun State
5. To ascertain the level of parental involvement of public secondary school students in Osun State

Research Questions

The research questions developed for the purpose of the study include:

1. What is the level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun State?
2. What is the level of parental education of public secondary school students in Osun State?
3. What is the nature of parental occupation of public secondary school students in Osun State?
4. What is the level of parental income of public secondary school students in Osun State?
5. What is the level of parental involvement of public secondary school students in Osun State?

Research hypothesis

The hypothesis developed and test is stated below:

1. There is a significant relative relationship between socio-economic factors and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Osun State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, the total number of respondents for this study is three thousand, three hundred and fifty (3,350) from a total of thirty-three thousand, four-hundred and ninety respondents. Multistage sampling technique was used to select the respondents for this study, proportionate to size sampling technique was used to select 10% of SS III students. The data collected in this study was coded and tested for completeness and then analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were analysed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation while hypothesis was tested using regression analysis. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: The level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Osun state

Subject	49% and below	Percentage (%)	50% and above	Percentage (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Mathematics	905	58%	655	42%	47.16	16.27	Low performance
English	881	56%	679	44%	47.36	18.26	Low performance

Source: Field 2024

Note: N=1560

Table 1 shows that academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Osun, in English and Mathematics is generally low. With a 42% credit pass rate in Mathematics and 44% credit pass rate in English, deductions can be made that students' performance in these key subjects leaves much to be desired. Furthermore, results from the table reveal a mean score of 47.16, which is lower than the credit pass mark of 50, therefore, it can be concluded that the general performance in Mathematics is low. Similarly, standard deviation of 16.27 in Mathematics shows that, out of 100 marks allocated, 68% of students scored between 31 and 63 which is indicative of the fact that many students struggled with the test. In the same vein, results of findings from English language revealed the mean score of 47.36- this is lower than the credit pass mark of 50, hence, conclusions can be drawn that there is an overall poor performance. Also, standard deviation of 18.26 in English is a pointer to the fact that, out of 100 marks allocated, 68% of students scored between 29 and 66 which is indicative of the fact that many students struggled with the test.

Table 2: The level of parental education of public secondary school students in Osun State

Highest Qualification	Fathers		Mothers	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Masters Degree	346	22.2%	443	28.4%
First Degree	1204	77.2%	1011	64.8%
SSCE	10	0.6%	106	6.8%
Total	1560	100%	1560	100%

Source: Field 2024

Results from table 2 reveal that 77.2% of fathers are first degree holders, this is followed by 22% master's degree holders and finally by SSCE holders- who constitute 0.6%. Meanwhile, 64.8% of mothers are first degree holders, 28.4% are master's holder and 6.8% are SSCE holders. Further conclusions can be drawn from the results that there are more graduates from the fathers when compared with mothers.

Table 3: The nature of parental occupation of public secondary school students in Osun State

Employment Status	Fathers		Mothers	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Employed (Public Sector)	184	11.8%	138	8.85%
Employed (Private Sector)	214	13.7%	830	53.21%
Self-employed (Business/Investor)	1161	74.4%	592	37.94%
Unemployed	1	0.1%	0	0%
Total	1560	100%	1560	50.09%

Source: Field 2024

It can be extrapolated from table 3 that owing to the 74.4% responses which favoured self-employed, most fathers are either business owners or investors, while 13.7% works with the private sector, while public sector has 11.8%. However, 53.21% of mothers are private sector workers, then 37.94% are self-employed, the remaining 8.85% are public sector workers. This means that there are more public sector and self-employed workers among the fathers when compared to the mothers, but mothers tilt more towards the private sector than fathers. The large proportion of fathers who work for themselves (74.4%) points to a robust entrepreneurial culture among fathers in Osun State.

Table 4: The level of parental income of public secondary school students in Osun State

Approximate income	Fathers		Mothers	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
#151,000-#300,000	235	15%	92	5.9%
#71,000-#150,000	606	38.8%	622	39.9%
Less than #70,000	719	46.2%	846	54.2%
Total	1560	100	1560	100

Source: Field 2024

From table 4 above, fathers are on the higher income scale, compared to mothers; considering 15% and 38.8% of the respondents earning between ₦151,000-₦300,000 and ₦71,000-₦150,000 respectively. While 5.9% and 39.9% of mothers

earn ₦151,000-₦300,000 and ₦71,000-₦150,000 respectively. Similarly, more mothers earn below ₦70,000 monthly; 54.2% and 46.2% for mothers and fathers respectively. According to findings, fathers are more likely to be in higher income bands than mothers, which is in line with recent research on the gender pay gap in Nigeria.

Table 5: The level of parental involvement of public secondary school students in Osun State

Item	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Σ	DECISION
I give career advice to my children regarding their academic goals and future professional aspirations.	215 (13.78%)	294 (18.85%)	480 (30.77%)	408 (21.15%)	163 (10.45%)	2.99	1.192	Involved
I attend my children's school events.	350 (22.44%)	369 (23.65%)	359 (23.01%)	268 (17.18%)	214 (13.72%)	3.24	1.341	Involved
I am involved in solving my children's academic-related social challenges	366 (23.46%)	370 (23.72%)	355 (22.76%)	228 (14.62%)	241 (15.44%)	3.25	1.370	Involved
I regularly communicate with my children's teachers about their academic performance and concerns.	282 (18.08%)	301 (19.29%)	414 (26.54%)	352 (22.56%)	211 (13.53%)	3.06	1.296	Involved
I am involved in monitoring my children's academic progress	259 (16.60%)	394 (25.26%)	474 (30.38%)	286 (18.33%)	147 (9.43%)	3.21	1.197	Involved
I manage my children's academic workload and help them deal with academic pressure	193 (12.37%)	278 (17.82%)	499 (31.99%)	428 (27.44%)	162 (10.38%)	2.94	1.166	Involved
I discuss my children's academic strengths and weaknesses with their teachers.	190 (12.18%)	275 (17.63%)	502 (32.18%)	431 (27.63%)	162 (10.38%)	2.94	1.163	Involved
I advise my children on their extra-curricular activities.	215 (13.78%)	294 (18.85%)	480 (30.77%)	408 (26.15%)	163 (10.45%)	2.99	1.192	Involved

Source: Field 2024

Note: N=1560, SA= Strongly Agree, A=Agree, N=Neutral, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree. Weighted average=2.70
 It can be extrapolated from table 5 above that all items on this section of the research instrument surpassed the mean average of 2.70, which is an indication that parents are in one way or the other involved in their children's education. In other words, parental involvement is high among public secondary school students in Osun State. This is corroborated by the responses which reveals that; parents give academic advise to their children, they attend school events such as career day and inter-house sporting activities.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 6: There is a relative relationship between socio-economic factors and the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Osun state

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Change Statistics				df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
			Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change				
1	.074 ^a	.006	-.002	.35625	.006	1.721	5	1554	.127	

a. Predictors: (Constant), CULT_NEW, OC_NEW, INC_NEW, LOIV_NEW, ED_NEW

Source: Field 2024

Results from table 6 reveal a weak relationship between socio-economic factors and academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Osun State. The model summary $F(5, 1554)=1.72$, $Adj R^2=0.002$ and $R^2=0.006$, indicates that the model is not statistically significant because there is a weak correlation between socio-economic factors and academic performance. Also, the beta coefficients $\beta=-0.037, -2.238, -0.095, 0.107, 0.205$ and $t= 1.020, -2.515, -1.211, 1.149, 2.635$ for income, education, occupation, level of involvement, and cultural beliefs reveal no significant relationship; with the exception of education and cultural variables with significant negative relationship and significant positive relationship respectively. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on academic performance revealed a low performance of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English. In addition to socio-economic factors, the pattern of underperformance could be laced with so many other causes, these include; the quality of teacher delivery and student motivation. Socio-economic status affects the capacity of a family to provide resources like extracurricular activities, private tutoring, and access to better educational options. In Nigeria, self-employed people tend to be highly autonomous and have unpredictable incomes; depending on how successful their businesses are, this could have a favorable or negative effect on their children's academic achievement. Also, the private sector has emerged as a significant employment option for women in Nigeria, especially in sectors like services, healthcare, and education where women are more likely to find permanent jobs.

Similarly, findings revealed that women are more likely to be employed in lower-paying positions, especially in the informal sector or lower echelons of the private sector, while men are more frequently found in higher-paying occupations in Nigeria, such as senior managerial positions and business ownership. The findings from the level of involvement showed how crucial parental support is in reducing academic stress, which is a problem that secondary school students face because of external and academic pressures. Parents play an active role in the education of their children, they are more likely to do well in school, have stronger social skills, and behave better. Parental involvement which includes helping with homework, establishing expectations for the children's education, and talking about future career objectives, greatly increases the motivation and achievement of the student.

For the hypothesis, research has consistently demonstrated that higher socio-economic status, specifically higher family income, parental education, and parental occupation, is associated with better academic outcomes. However, the findings in Osun State differ from this overall tendency, since the poor correlation shows that these characteristics have negligible impact on the academic achievement of students in the state. So many reasons could be adduced to these findings, dearth of teaching facilities, poor teacher quality and poor perception of education. The significant positive relationship between cultural beliefs and academic performance is a pointer to the fact that culture plays a significant role in influencing students' academic performance. Hard-work and respect which are key cultural values are positive contributors to students' learning attitude, which ultimately culminates into better academic performance.

While parental involvement is considered to be a strong predictor for academic success, the lack of significance from the findings could be as a result of the way parents get involved. For example, the effectiveness of parental involvement could be greatly limited by their educational attainment and lack of proper understanding of the school curriculum- which could lead to a misinterpretation. Meanwhile in rural areas, parental involvement may take non-traditional forms which not easily measured by conventional or standardised scales. Finally, results revealed that there is no significant relationship between parental occupation and academic performance. This could be as a result of the fact that financial stability or availability of educational resources may not have a direct relationship with occupational status. This therefore, explains why occupations does not have a significant relationship with academic performance of students in this perspective.

Conclusion

The unique educational problems in Osun State, such as inadequate school facilities and low-quality teachers, greatly reduce the influence of parental socioeconomic characteristics. Also, cultural norms that emphasise diligence and decency were found to have a greater impact on academic achievement. The study also noted that traditional measures of parental involvement may not fully capture the ways parents in rural areas contribute to their children's education.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations made:

1. Educational authorities should focus on enhancing the qualifications and teaching methodologies of teachers, particularly in core subjects like English and Mathematics.
2. Also, governments and policymakers should ensure that schools in Osun State are adequately equipped with teaching materials and infrastructure to support effective learning.
3. In the same vein, programs aimed at improving parents' understanding of the school curriculum should be introduced, allowing them to better support their children's education.
4. Finally, financial planning and support initiatives could be introduced for self-employed parents to mitigate the economic uncertainties associated with their occupation and provide stable financial support for their children's education.

References

- Anthony Kudjo Donkor. (2023). Parental Involvement in Education in Ghana: The Case of a Private Elementary School. *International Journal about Parents in Education*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.54195/ijpe.18166>
- Arifin, A. Z., Azizah, F. R., Putri, M., Afiah, N., Rohanah, R., Rosaninda, R., & Holiah, I. (2023). Relationship of Parents' Socio-Economic Status to Student Achievement. *Journal of Education and Teacher Training Innovation*, 1(1), 53–59. <https://doi.org/10.61227/jetti.v1i1.11>
- Bhatia, A., Rana, S., & Gregor, M. (2023). The Relationship Between Parental Attachment and Career Aspirations in Indian Female Undergraduate Students. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 10690727221129615. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10690727221129615>
- Chavez, J. V., Adalia, H. G., Alberto, J. P., Chavez, J. V., Adalia, H. G., & Alberto, J. P. (2023). Parental support strategies and motivation in aiding their children learn the English language. *Forum for Linguistic Studies*, 5(2), 1541. <https://doi.org/10.59400/fls.v5i2.1541>
- Cheng, A., & Lai, C. (2023). Parental stress in families of children with special educational needs: a systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 14(14). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1198302>
- Colicol, F. L., & Sali-Latif, F. K. (2023). Parental Occupation, Social Class, and School Choice in Southern Philippines: Their Implications to Educational Public-Private Partnership vis-à-vis the K-12 SHS Voucher Program. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(6), 345–369. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.22.6.19>
- Covas, F., & Veiga, F. H. (2021). Student engagement in Higher Education, age and parental education level. *Estudos de Psicologia (Campinas)*, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-0275202138e200020>
- Duckworth, A. L., Taxer, J. L., Eskreis-Winkler, L., Galla, B. M., & Gross, J. J. (2019). Self-Control and Academic Achievement. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 70(1), 373–399. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010418-103230>
- Efstratopoulou, M., Sofologi, M., Giannoglou, S., & Bonti, E. (2022). Parental Stress and Children's Self-Regulation Problems in Families with Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). *Journal of Intelligence*, 10(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence10010004>
- Eliasson, K., Haapanen, M., & Westerlund, O. (2020). Regional concentration of university graduates: The role of high school grades and parental background. *European Urban and Regional Studies*, 27(4), 398–414. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969776420923133>
- Eyinade, G. (2020). Assessment of Career Ambition of Head of Farm Families for their Children: A Case of Farmers in South Western Nigeria. *the Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 6(2), 127–132.
- Georgiou, S. N. (2023). Parental involvement: beyond demographics. *International Journal about Parents in Education*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.54195/ijpe.18250>
- Guttfleisch, T., & Kogan, I. (2022). Parental Occupation and Students' STEM Achievements by Gender and Ethnic Origin: Evidence from Germany. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 100735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rssm.2022.100735>
- Guttormsen, D., & Moore, F. (2023). [‘Thinking About How We Think’: Using Bourdieu’s Epistemic Reflexivity to Reduce Bias in International Business Research](https://doi.org/10.54195/ijpe.18250). *Management International Review*, 63, 531-559.
- Hsieh, M. (2022). The Relationships Between Home-Based Parental Involvement, Study Habits and Academic Achievement among Adolescents. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, 43(2), 027243162211015. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02724316221101527>
- Hsieh, T., & Simpkins, S. D. (2022). Longitudinal associations between parent degree/occupation, parent support, and adolescent motivational beliefs in STEM. *Journal of Adolescence*, 94(5), 728–747. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jad.12059>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259882>

- Kainuwa, A., Binti, N., Yusuf, M., & Saibon, J. (2018). Relationship between Parental Cultural and Religious Beliefs and Students' Dropout from Government Secondary Schools of Zamfara, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 23(1), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2301092937>
- Kim, H., Kang, H.-W., Choi, J.-Y., & Cho, S.-I. (2023). Trends in adolescent secondhand smoke exposure at home over 15 years in Korea: Inequality by parental education level. *Tobacco Induced Diseases*, 21(June), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.18332/tid/166132>
- Meng, Q., & Zhang, Q. (2023). [The Influence of Academic Self-Efficacy on University Students' Academic Performance: The Mediating Effect of Academic Engagement](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259882).
- Mudassir, I. U., & Abubakar, N. B. (2015). The Impact of Parents' Occupation on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Kuala Terengganu. *Multilingual Academic Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.6007/majess/v3-i1/1899>
- Naite, I. (2021). Impact of Parental Involvement on Children's Academic Performance at Crescent International School, Bangkok, Thailand. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 690(1), 012064. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/690/1/012064>
- National Bureau of Statistics NBS (2022). *WAEC result statistics report for 2019-2021*
- Ohanyelu, C. (2022). Family Background as an Indicator of Students' Academic Achievement in Science Subjects among High School Students in Nigeria. *American Journal of Arts and Educational Administration Research*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.58314/089897>
- Oni, J. O. et al., (2016) Enhancing access to and quality of basic education through head teachers' leadership functions. Lagos
- Rahaman, A. (2023). Influences of parental occupation on children's occupational choices. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 50(12), 1735–1755. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/eme/ijsepp/ijse-10-2022-0705.html>
- Rana, M. A. Khan, Nadeem, I., & Tasneem. (2015). The influence of Parents Educational level on Secondary School Students Academic achievements in District Rajanpur. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(16), 76–79.
- Tipton, M. (2018). An investigation into children's gender stereotypes and the effect they have on children's career aspirations. *The STeP Journal: Student Teacher Perspectives*, 50–63. <https://insight.cumbria.ac.uk/id/eprint/4010>
- Umoru, S., & Aboritoli, S. (2021). A STUDY OF PARENTAL ATTITUDE TOWARDS MATHEMATICS EDUCATION AND STUDENTS MATH HOMEWORK BEHAVIOR. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 9(5), 366–371. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/12846>
- Yulianti, K., Denessen, E., & Droop, M. (2018). The effects of parental involvement on children's education: a study in elementary schools in Indonesia. *International Journal about Parents in Education*, 10, 14–32. <https://doi.org/10.54195/ijpe.14123>
- Yusuf, M., & Adeoye, M. (2014). Entrepreneurship education in Nigeria: Issues and challenges. *International Journal of Educational Management and Research*, 3(5), 7–14.